

Investigations for the improvement of the Cyber Security
using Cloud Computing methods and Architecture

SYNOPSIS

Of

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TOPIC OF THE THESIS

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SYNOPSIS

In today's world, the wireless technology and Internet of things plays important role, the mobile devices like smart phones, mobile devices etc needs different wireless access. Hence the requirement of bandwidth and the computation of network also get increased rapidly. The mobile devices becoming smarter and intelligent and it further require many computation servers. The development of these applications is getting limited because of finite computation service. In addition, this computation causes more delay and this delay is not suitable for the devices or application which is more delay sensitive.

Considering the collaborative service cache strategy of storing such as storing demand among mobile users, the data size and the required computation capacity of task in service cache using MCC (e.g., the Increasing cache services in Mobile Cloud Computing and online intermediate storing processing have different storage and CPU requirements) and the Mobile Cloud Computing and storage constraints of Cloud in 5G cellular network, Maintain the energy in Cloud clouding is challenging problem. The main problem in caching is content caching and task caching therefore based on the caching method server should assign. Still Cloud with server setup not able to catch and store all type of computation storage. Normally Collaborative resource allocation method is defined in cache technique with three classification Voice User, data User, and Offloading user. Normal user adopts with spectrum utilization and data user generates utility due to spectrum and cache. Offloading user generates utility due to spectrum and computational resource. Every Base Station is connected with Mobile Cloud Computing Server around this earth. The analysis finally leads to the development of the concept of 'Universal Technology' model.

Ideal properties of a device or a system can be used to upgrade or improve its properties towards reaching 100% efficiency. By comparing the properties/characteristics of a practical for Computational taskoffloading and which is not consider the virtualization with interference in Neighbor Cloud to handle Interference issue

In the processing of data offloading in multiple users and multiple servers, Mobile Cloud computing task can be processed on Cloud or locally in 5G Cellular network. Though, when the 5G cellular task is cached in the Cloud, it may not need to be processed locally in advance

network. Based on the deciding task how much task to offloading is challenging issue.

Thereafter, it is challenging to make a task offloading in data with task caching using advanced network.

Mobile Cloud Computing Optimization problem in 5G cellular network: When computing and storage resources at Cloud are limited, how to give task caching and offloading problem and solve this problem is challenging issue. This is because Mobile Energy Cloud computing multiple energy task caching and offloading scheme needs careful coordination

Mobile Cloud Computing is developing recent years which provides this computation without delay and high performance by deploying Cloud servers in the mobile network. The Cloud servers compute the user requirement within fraction of second and it is very suitable for delay sensitive tasks. In order to decrease the delay and energy used for a computation the mobile Cloud computing requires two important aspects and they are

- Cloud Caching
- Task Offloading

Cloud caching application data is revealed and easy to access through unauthorized one. Cloud Cache data has threat from hackers and leaking information

Cloud Caching:

Cloud Caching is also known as content offloading. The Modern world variety of technologies available to improve the application and user application response. To reduce the delay and energy the important content cached in the Cloud. The server uses the content from the cache so that the time and energy required to get details from the device reduces.

Task offloading:

This is important task in the mobile Cloud computing. When and where the task needs to be offloaded from the user device to the mobile Cloud to save energy and time is called task offloading. The main problem in the Mobile Cloud computing is storage capacity of the Cloud. The storage capacity of the Cloud is very less. But the computation and the storage capacity should be large comparatively to perform the task offloading. In practical the hardware and software resources to perform the computation and storage is lesser than the assumption.

Statement of the Problem

Open source in MCC, a user task has to be controlled to be offloaded to the right Mobile Cloud server with cache, in remote MCC, to get served. This offloading is facing a problem while finding the server and problem in service cache. There will be less implementation in service side

and secure cache performance. In which server will be position to get the traffic and maintain the secure cache. Since we are facing problems in application security and delay time for responding. These are a need to develop the solution to fulfill all the problems mentioned in the research. Maintain the energy of the system will be tough one due to the task offloading.

Problem of Secure Task Caching:

Each task required by the various mobile devices will be different and their computations requirements also are different, so the heterogeneity of the task and the computation require more cache space which is challenging face for the Cloud secure server.

Problem of Secure Task Offloading:

When a computing task is assigned on the Cloud server, the Cloud server computes it locally. But if the task is cached in the Cloud the task need not to be performed locally. Hence the task offloading decision is a challenging task to make the system in secure and energy efficient.

Security Caching and offloading is a big challenging issue in Mobile Cloud Computing. Because of the limited storage we need to carefully handle this problem of task offloading and task cache which in turn decreases the energy consumed. The offloading cache task is challenging one since cache pollution attack is disseminated throughout the network which will be threat for secure communication.

How to solve the problem?

The mobile Cloud computing has many servers and each server maintains a small cache storage system. When the task is received by the server, the server searches in its cache whether the cache has related task id, if the server has the task the task is performed from the cache and task is completed on the server. If the server does not have the id, then the task id is broadcasted to the nearby servers. And the servers search in its own cache storage system. If any one of the cache has the relates task then the server gives positive acknowledgement to the server which has the task. Then the server shares the task to the server which gave the positive acknowledgement. Hence the task is computed and returned the result. Thereby we reduce the energy of computation and task offloading. All the new tasks are not stored in the cache memory and so cache space is also used efficiently.

1. Appropriate use of these security standards can benefit your application greatly, improving security and response times and reducing server load
2. We are implemented with servers which can optionally have a local server with in-line cache. This optional server cache independent data grid on each server, which maintain serving cache for server-side cache. This is called near server-side cache. A server-side cache is fast because it supports in line memory content for entire cached data which is stored remotely

3. We will apply the above-mentioned method to save time and energy, bandwidth consumption etc even searching on nearby servers takes less time and consume less energy as compare to sending task directly on main cloud datacenter.

Security Analysis & Metrics Consideration:

On the sequence of URL naming followed by hierarchal naming which consists of many components. The routing performance will be done through name-based contents to deliver subscribers. The Cache Pollution attack is vulnerable to different method which filled the polluted files in cache system. Contrary most of time the cache pollution attack could not be monitored where the attack is in progress or not. The communication system denies the services from routers which indicates the attack occurred even then communication is happening through routers. We have proposed the DES Cache System (Discrete Event Simulator) measure experimental cache parameters through the policies Least Frequency Used, Least Recently, Variable Data Used and Multiple attacker Behaviors. The number attackers will send unpopular request files from different ISP must pollute the nearby nodes which affect regular consumer nodes through normal request from Router cache. Normally name based router will attain 85% to 90% hit ratio and the client normal request entry will be 1Mbyte ,Consider a normal internet architecture using Link rate is 1Gbps ,data access rate between the communication 100 Mbps and Cache size is 100Gbytes.The normal detection scheme will access the subscriber communication data ranges and identify the security services and network unique attributes.

Chapter 1 contains the discussion on the main problem in caching is content caching and task caching therefore based on the caching method server should assign. Still Cloud with server setup not able to catch and store all type of computation storage. Normally Collaborative resource allocation method is defined in cache technique with three classification Voice User, data User, and Offloading user. Normal user adopts with spectrum utilization and data user generates utility due to spectrum and cache. Offloading user generates utility due to spectrum and computational resource. Every Base Station is connected with Mobile Cloud Computing Server for Computational task offloading and which is not consider the virtualization with interference in Neighbor Cloud to handle Interference issue Chapter 1 also contains the research objective, research design, and research methodology used in the Thesis. This innovative work contains experimental oriented results with simulation carried out on new conceptual model results developed.

Chapter 2 contains statement of the problemOpen source in MCC; a user task has to be controlled to be offloaded to the right Mobile Cloud server with cache, in remote MCC, to get served. This offloading is facing a problem while finding the server and problem in service cache. There will

be less implementation in service side and secure cache performance. In which server will be position to get the traffic and maintain the secure cache. Since we are facing problems in application security and delay time for responding. These are a need to develop the solution to fulfill all the problems mentioned in the research. Maintain the energy of the system will be tough one due to the task offloading.

Chapter 3 contains LITERATURE SURVEY related to the concept of There are numerous Cyber security systems that have been proposed by scholars. In recent year research analysis with results has been provided in form of literature survey and concluded the existing experiments in cyber security mobile cloud computing.

In chapter 4, the concept of related work the increased mobile traffic, mostly multimedia demand which includes Audio, video and gaming are produced by smart phones or other end devices can produce a lot of congestion on the core network. Typical IP protocols won't work efficiently in term of QoE, delay and throughput. Mobile Cloud Computing ICN can provide these services in an efficient mannerit support's naming scheme in which user is transparent to the underlying processes (e.g. location of processes/server), user is concerned with high level name.

In chapter 5, the experimental search in cloud computing the phenomenon of Cloud Computing is very promising which ensures businesses increase efficiency alongside reducing their cost of production. Data protection and security in cloud computing is still crawling on its knees and needs more research attention although it has been deployed and used in production environment.

Chapter 6 contains various results including simulation results. The encrypted data are transferred from the access point to cloud's database. In cloud the data is stored in a central database.

In chapter 7, the concept of ideal software, its realization scenarios, and opportunity for realizing the ideal computing system using cloud computing model are proposed, discussed and analyzed.

In chapter 8, conclusion Cloud computing is the emerging technology in upcoming IT generation. One of the hurdles and barrier in cloud computing is privacy and security issues. Any developing organization need to store the data that need to reduce the storage cost is mandatory. So that the data helps them in many decision making systems.

Finally, Chapter 9 contains experimental code and References.

Entire Thesis is based on the concept of a unique research model to identify the gap between ideal system/technology and present system/technology and to identify opportunities to minimize the gap to improve the system/technology towards ideal level. In this innovative research work introduced Constant Interval Frequency Used Policy that would provide time frame for access

link delay connecting the routers and subscribers through this Constant Interval we could have find the attacks. Also investigated on the new Optimization on 5G SDN approach in order to route the requests to the proper MCC server instance. 5G SDN organized by routing information based on the content offloading. Te advantages of 5G SDN for Cloud computing services have been presented in works. In our case, the MCC server Optimization scheme messaging to communicate final devices with the structure. Therefore, the transport is delegated to web Application. To unload the 5G SDN controller from that burden, web Application proxies are collocated at the MCC servers, proactive 5G SDN the deployment of specific caching software. Te adopted approach relies on already routing is performed to direct requests to the nearest proxy from the 5G SDN controller entry point. An equivalent approach is presented in. 5G SDN controller is deployed on the same MCC server instance as the proxy and near to the 5G SDN entry points. The instance decides the Optimization unit to which the request will be directed and programs the path to that MCC server. The 5G SDN controller installs the flows to redirect the request from the proxy to the proper Optimization unit which is in the same MCC server instance in this case. When the Optimization unit calculates the fix, the result is returned through the proxy to the user. (ii) Te second request is a user searching request, indicated as location. User, which is issued by an external application. This request arrives directly to the nearest web Application proxy. (iii) When the UE change to another AN, requests are addressed to a different local MCC server to compute the location as above. Notifications of user Optimization from intelligent infrastructures are not included. The 5G SDN controller redirects the requests to the nearest MCC server instance’s web Application proxy of the last user’s known Optimization. For the moment, our implementation routes the request to the nearest Optimization unit to the entry web Application proxy, with the aim of reducing the response delay

The Thesis is prepared by combining the 32 published papers under the single Project “**Research on the Improvement of the Cyber Security using Cloud Computing**” on the broad area of ‘**Computer Science and Engineering**’. This post-doctoral project includes both aspects of research - creating new knowledge and new interpretation of existing knowledge through systematic analysis.

Published Papers Considered Chapter wise:

Chapter 1 :Introduction

1. Cloud security: risk factors and security issues in current trends Dr.K.Sai Manoj International Journal of Engineering & Technology, Science Publishing Corporation October 2019 (Scopus) (Single Author) <https://www.sciencepubco.com/index.php/ijet/issue/view/495> (Indexed in German National Serials Database (ZDB) (Germany), ProQuest (USA) etc)
2. Conceptual Oriented Analysis on the Security based on the SaaS Cloud Computing Architecture for the Cyber Security Issues by Dr.K.Sai Manoj published in International Journal for Research in Applied Science & Engineering Technology (IJRASET) ISSN: 2321-9653; IC Value: 45.98; SJ Impact Factor: 7.177, Volume 7, Issue VII, July 2019. (First Author) <https://www.ijraset.com/files/serve.php?FID=24254>

Chapter 2 : Statement of the Problem

3. Risk Factors and Security Issues in Various Cloud Storage Operations Dr.K.Sai Manoj Volume-8, Issue-12, October 2019, ISSN: 2278-3075 (Online) Published By: Blue Eyes Intelligence Engineering & Sciences Publication (First Author) (Elsevier Scopus)
4. Data Mining and Machine Learning Techniques for Cyber Security Intrusion Detection International Journal of Engineering and Advanced Technology (IJEAT) Dr.K.Sai Manoj Dr.P.S.Aithal ISSN: 2249 – 8958, Volume-9 Issue-3, February, 2020 <https://www.ijeat.org/download/volume-9-issue-3/>
5. Blockchain Cyber Security Vulnerabilities and Potential Counter measures International Journal of Innovative Technology and Exploring Engineering (IJITEE) Dr.K.Sai Manoj Dr.P.S.Aithal ISSN: 2278-3075, Volume-9 Issue-5, March 2020 <http://www.ijitee.org/wp-content/uploads/papers/v9i5/E2170039520.pdf>

Chapter 3 :Literature Survey

6. CHALLENGING ISSUES RELATED TO SOME SPECIFIC IMPORTANT PROBLEMS IN THE CLOUD PLATFORM by Dr.K.Sai Manoj published in the merit list by International Journal of Computer Engineering and Applications Volume XIII, Issue VIII JAN 2020. (UGC Approved Journal with Thomson researcher id) (Single author)
7. Conceptual Oriented Analysis On The Industrial Standard Cyber Security by Dr.K.Sai Manoj published in International Journal of Computer Science Trends and Technology (IJCST) – Volume 7, Issue 4, Jul - Aug 2019 (Single Author) <http://www.ijcstjournal.org/volume-7/issue-4/IJCST-V7I4P3.pdf>

8. CONCEPTUAL ORIENTED ANALYSIS ON THE IMPACT ON THE CLOUD SECURITY ON THE CYBER ATTACKS by Dr.K.Sai Manoj selected in the merit list by Journal of Analysis and Computation (JAC) (An International Peer Reviewed Journal), www.ijaonline.com, ISSN 0973-2861 Volume XII, Issue I, May 2019 (First Author) <http://www.ijaonline.com/conceptual-oriented-analysis-impact-cloud-security-cyber-attacks/>
9. INVESTIGATIONS ON THE CLOUD DATA STORAGE SECURITY BASED USING DIFFIE HELLMAN ALGORITHM by Dr.K.Sai Manoj selected in the merit list by International Journal of Computer Engineering and Applications, Volume XIII, Issue VI, JUNE. 19, www.ijcea.com ISSN 2321-3469 (First Author) <http://www.ijcea.com/investigations-cloud-data-storage-security-based-using-diffie-hellman-algorithm/>
10. Analysis of the Technique for the Improvement of the Data Confidentiality in the Cloud Computing Environment by Dr.K.Sai Manoj Published in international Journal of Computer Science Trends and Technology (IJCST) – Volume 7 Issue 4, Jul - Aug 2019 (First Author) <http://www.ijcstjournal.org/volume-7/issue-4/IJCST-V7I4P5.pdf>
11. Conceptual oriented analysis on the modern tools and techniques to Enrich Security Vulnerabilities in Ethical Hacking Dr.K.Sai Manoj International Journal of Computer Science Trends and Technology (IJCST) in May-June 2019, Volume Number 7 Issue3 with ISSN: 2347-8578 & ISO 3297:2007.This Journal has Thomson Reuters ResearcherID: M-3066-2016. (First Author) <http://www.ijcstjournal.org/volume-7/issue-3/IJCST-V7I3P25.pdf>
12. Investigation on the Cloud Computing in terms of the current trends and also to meet the important challenges with security for the improvement of the Health care services Dr.K.Sai Manoj IJCEA Feb. 2019, with Thomson Reuters Research Id: P1671-2016. Also It is UGC approved Journal. For this article author Dr.K.Sai Manoj research article in the merit list from the Reviewers and Editorial Team. (First Author) <http://www.ijcea.com/investigation-cloud-computing-terms-current-trends-also-meet-important-challenges-security-improvement-health-care-services/>
13. Investigation on the security aspects of the cloud computing using symmetric and asymmetric algorithms, Dr.K.Sai Manoj International Journal of Computer Engineering and Applications, Volume XIII, Issue I, January. 19, www.ijcea.com ISSN 2321-3469 with Thomson Reuters Research Id: P1671-2016. Also It is UGC approved Journal. For this article author Dr.K.Sai Manoj received appreciation certificate in the merit list from the Editor. (First Author) <http://www.ijcea.com/investigation-security-aspects-cloud-computing-using-symmetric-asymmetric-algorithms/>
14. Investigation on the Attribute Based Encryption for Secure Data Access in Cloud, Dr.K.Sai Manoj International Journal of Computer Science Trends and Technology (IJCST) with

Thomson Reuters Researcher ID: M-3066-2016 – Volume 6 Issue 6, Nov-Dec 2018. ISSN: 2347-8578 (First Author) <https://www.scribd.com/document/393639933/IJCST-V6I6P13-Dr-K-SAI-MANOJ-MS-K-Mrudula-Mrs-K-Maanasa-K-Phani-Srinivas>

15. INVESTIGATION ON THE DATA SECURITY IN CLOUD COMPUTING USING BIOMETRICS International journal of current advanced research UGC approved and also Thomson Reuters journal with researcher id and END NOTE ISSN: O: 2319-6475, ISSN: P: 2319-65, Impact factor: 6.614, Volume 7; Issue 12(B); December 2018; Page No. 16473-16475. (First Author) <http://journalijcar.org/issues/investigation-data-security-cloud-computing-using-biometrics>.

Chapter 4 : Related Work

16. Investigation on the Data Protection in the Cloud using Predicate Based Encryption International Journal of Computer Science and Information Technology Research UGC approved with ISSN 2348-120X (online) Vol. 6, Issue 4, pp: (61-65), Month: October - December 2018. (First Author) <http://www.researchpublish.com/journal/IJCSITR/Issue-4-October-2018-December-2018/0>

17. Content Filtering and cloud based intrusion detection system, Dr.K.Sai Manoj, Global Journal of Engineering Science and Research Management – January 2018 (First Author – Thomson Reuters)

18. A Survey on Protection of Multimedia Content in Cloud Computing, Dr. K.Sai Manoj, MrudulaKudaravalli, International Journal of Computer Science and Mobile Computing - Vol.6 Issue.11, November-2017, pg.7-11 (First Author) <http://ijcsmc.com/docs/papers/November2017/V6I11201705.pdf>

Chapter 5 : Experimental Search in Cloud Computing

19. Research on Security and Vulnerabilities of Blockchain Systems by Dr.K.Sai Manoj published in International Journal for Research in Applied Science & Engineering Technology (IJRASET) ISSN: 2321-9653; IC Value: 45.98; SJ Impact Factor: 7.177 Volume 8 Issue I, Jan 2020 (Single Author) <https://www.ijraset.com/files/serve.php?FID=26233>

20. A Study on identifying defects and solutions of search engines, Dr.K.Sai Manoj, Global Journal of Engineering Science and Research Management – January 2018 (Second Author)

21. INVESTIGATION ON THE ON THE CLOUD COMPUTING SECURITY USING PET AND REMOTE ATTESTATION IN CLOUD ARCHITECTURES by Dr.K.Sai Manoj published in International Journal of Current Advanced Research Volume 8; Issue 10 (D); October 2019 <http://dx.doi.org/10.24327/ijcar.2019> Impact Factor: 6.614 ISSN: O: 2319-6475,

Chapter 6 : Analysis of the Cloud Computing

22. Conceptual based on the Data Mining Techniques for the Prediction of Hydration Assessment, Breath Analysis and Heart Disease International Journal of Innovative Technology and Exploring Engineering (IJITEE) Dr.K.Sai Manoj ISSN: 2278-3075, Volume-8 Issue-12S2, October 2019 <http://www.ijitee.org/wp-content/uploads/papers/v8i12S2/L107510812S219.pdf> (First Author)

23. Research on the Security Policies for Cloud Computing International Journal of Innovative Technology and Exploring Engineering (IJITEE) Dr.K.Sai Manoj ISSN: 2278-3075, Volume-8 Issue12,October2019(FirstAuthor)<http://www.ijitee.org/wpcontent/uploads/papers/v8i12S2/L107610812S219.pdf>

24. Design and Development of Various Cloud Computing Architectures Improving the Security International Journal of Innovative Technology and Exploring Engineering (IJITEE) Dr.K.Sai Manoj ISSN: 2278-3075, Volume-8 Issue-12S2, October 2019 (First Author)

Chapter 7 : Results and Discussions

25. **Faster content sharing over smart phone** based Delay- tolerant networks. Dr. Sai Manoj Kudaravalli, International Journal of Engineering Research- Online. Vol.5,Issue.4,2017,ISSN: 2321-7758. July-Aug. Article available online <http://www.ijor.in>; (First Author)

26. An Efficient and Novel Approach Using T.H.E.S Methodology for CBIR, Dr. Sai Manoj Kudaravalli, International journal of computer science Mechatronics. SJIF-4.454|Vol.3.Issue .5.2017. ISSN: 2455-1910. (Second Author)

27. **SOA Based CAM Cloud- Assisted Privacy** Preserving Mobile Health Monitoring, Dr. Sai Manoj Kudaravalli, International journal of computer science Mechatronics. SJIF-4.454|Vol.3.Issue .6.2017. ISSN: 2455-1910. (First Author)

Chapter 8 :Conclusion

28. UNCRACKABLE CIPHER DYNAMIC DOUBLE ENCRYPTION STANDARD IN CLOUD FOR DATA ACCESS CONTROL AND PRIVACY PRESERVING MECHANISM Dr. K. Sai Manoj, World Journal of Engineering Research and Technology WJERT 2019, Vol. 5,Issue6,43745(FirstAuthor)https://www.wjert.org/admin/assets/article_issue/35102019/1575371428.pdf

29. **Conceptual oriented study on the cloud computing architecture for the full-security**, Dr.K.SaiManoj International Journal of Engineering & Technology, Science Publishing Corporation (SPC) <https://www.sciencepubco.com/index.php/ijet/article/view/11654> (First Author)
30. A Study on Data Controller-Preserving Public Auditing for Secured Cloud Storage, Dr. K. Sai Manoj, International Journal of Modern Engineering Research (First Author) [http://www.ijmer.com/pages/Vol.8-Iss.1\(Versio-1\).html](http://www.ijmer.com/pages/Vol.8-Iss.1(Versio-1).html)

Chapter 9 :Experimental code and References

31. **SOA Based CAM Cloud- Assisted Privacy** Preserving Mobile Health Monitoring, Dr. Sai Manoj Kudaravalli, International journal of computer science Mechatronics. SJIF-4.454|Vol.3.Issue.6.2017. ISSN: 2455-1910. (First Author)
32. **Faster content sharing over smart phone** based Delay- tolerant networks. Dr. Sai Manoj Kudaravalli, International Journal of Engineering Research- Online. Vol.5,Issue.4,2017,ISSN: 2321-7758. July-Aug. Article available online <http://www.ijor.in>;

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